

INFORMATION AND ANALYTICAL ASSESSMENT OF ACCIDENT RISK IN ROAD TRAFFIC

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Abstract. *This article presents the findings of a study on the information and analytical assessment of road traffic accident risks in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The research employed a comprehensive approach to examine road accidents from multiple perspectives and incorporate the viewpoints of all relevant stakeholders. The methodology combined both qualitative and quantitative analyses. Special emphasis was placed on developing recommendations to reduce risks associated with human factors, vehicle condition, road infrastructure, and environmental influences. The application of the Smeed method helped establish the correlation between social and transport risks, shedding light on the current traffic situation that required particular attention. The Q-Cochran method was used to organize drivers' opinions, revealing the subjective aspects of risk perception, such as dangerous driving maneuvers, speeding, and poor visibility on the roads. The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), based on expert evaluation, helped identify priority areas for improving road safety. The analysis identified critical factors, including the quality of road surfaces, the presence of clear markings and signage, and the adequacy of lighting in high-traffic areas. Proposed measures include the installation of additional passive safety features, the creation of pedestrian crossings with warning systems, and the introduction of intelligent traffic management technologies. Overall, the study's findings provide a solid foundation for developing an effective strategy to reduce road accidents. The suggested measures include enhancing driver education, upgrading road infrastructure, integrating innovative technologies in traffic management, and strengthening enforcement of traffic laws.*

Keywords: *road accidents, road injuries, Smeed's method, Q-test Cochran's, Manchester Driver Questionnaire, analytical hierarchy method, expert panel.*

INTRODUCTION

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the economy and production, including the demand for road transport, are developing at a high rate, primarily the demand for road transport, which connects all sectors of a single economic mechanism. The interests of the development of society and production processes in the country require further improvement in the efficiency of vehicles, which in turn is directly related to improving road safety.

In the world, traffic accidents are the second leading cause of serious injury after criminal injuries. During the year, up to 1.3 million people become victims of road accidents, and up to 50 million received injuries of varying degrees [1]. Low- and middle-income countries account for approximately 60% of global road transport and 93% of all fatal road accidents. Road traffic injuries are the leading cause of death for children and young people aged 5 to 29. In many countries, road traffic damage accounts for 3% of their gross domestic product [2].

Worldwide, the issue of improving road safety is considered relevant not only because of the importance of the health and life of every person in the country, but also because he suffers

financial losses in the economy due to long-term social losses. Therefore, in order to implement more effective measures to improve road safety, it is important to timely assess the risk of road accidents and reduce it, taking into account the characteristics of the factors of road accidents, the behavior of road users, and the interaction of factors.

The results of a detailed study of the set of measures implemented in the field of road safety in our republic indicate the presence of a number of problems, in particular, the lack of effective models for assessing the risk of road accidents for optimal regulation of individual requirements for roads, vehicles, road users, as well as other infrastructure elements. According to the Road Safety Service of the Department of Public Safety under the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an average of 9-10 thousand accidents occurs annually, including more than 2 thousands of them with human casualties, including in 2021 compared to 2020, the number of road accidents increased by 43.24%, and the number of deaths in car accidents increased by 23.65%. In 2021, the number of victims of road accidents amounted to 2426 people (of which 263 children), and the number of victims - 9230 people (Figure 1). Identifying and analyzing factors that significantly affect the likelihood of road accidents and the severity of their consequences, as well as the impact on them by identifying general patterns and causes of road accidents, predicting the likelihood of their occurrence and assessing the severity of them, significantly increase road safety [3].

Figure 1. Information on road accidents in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2009-2022.

On average, about 2,000 people die on the roads of the Republic of Uzbekistan every year [4]. This indicator does not decrease over the years. According to the traffic safety service of the Department of Public Safety under the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the death toll from accidents in 2021 increased by 23.65% compared to 2020 (Figure 1).

As can be seen from the above indicators, the issue of the risk of death of people in road traffic is relevant, since it is necessary to take into account the basic safety requirements associated with the following risks on roads: the transport and operational condition of the road, roadside and dividing strips, traffic management equipment, road fences, road facilities, artificial lighting devices, etc.

Since, today, road traffic injuries and mortality from a traffic accident are recognized as one of the most important problems of modern society. It is known that many factors affect the occurrence of road accidents. According to the Haddon matrix [5], the significance of risk factors in accidents is divided into three stages: before the accident, during and after the accident, and into three groups of factors: person, vehicle and environment (Table 1).

Table 1. Haddon matrix.

Phase		Factors dependent on:		
		Human	Vehicle and road	Environment
Before the accident	Accident prevention	Knowledge Behavioral attitudes Health problems Police control	Roadworthiness Road lighting Brake system condition Compliance with the speed limit	Road section and condition Speed limits Pedestrian structures and devices
At the time of the accident	Injury prevention during an accident	Use of seat belts Health problems	Availability and use of seat belts by passengers Other safety devices Emergency vehicle design	Road objects preventing accidents
After the accident	Maintaining life	First aid skills Availability of health care	Easy access to the scene Fire risk	Availability of rescue services Traffic congestion

It was revealed that the lack of modern information and analytical methods makes it difficult to correctly assess the current state of road safety in the Republic of Uzbekistan. This study addresses this issue.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, we have selected the most new methods of information and analytical assessment of the risk of accidents in road traffic. When comparing the death toll from accidents with the public, the risk of death is relatively low. Not all segments of the population may be road users, but drivers are directly the main road users. This comparison shows us the dependence of the mortality rate as a result of road accidents in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the number of direct road users (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Relationship of social and transport risk.

Most accidents are directly related to the human factor. Driving skills and driving style, that is, driver behavior, can be considered as the main factor in driving a car. Analyzing foreign research, it was found that the Manchester Driver Questionnaire method [6,7] helps to identify and assess important factors on the road through driver behavior. With this method, it is possible to

assess the factors influencing road deaths from the point of view of drivers as direct participants and major road users.

Therefore, one of the main directions of this study is the method of information and analytical assessment of the risk of road accidents by conducting a survey among drivers. This approach involved collecting data directly from drivers through surveys and analyzing them to identify risk factors and improve road safety. Below are some of the main aspects and methods I have used in this direction [8,9,10]:

1. Survey project. Effective survey design is critical to generating accurate and meaningful data. A questionnaire was developed containing a range of questions relating to driver behaviour, attitudes, driving experience, risk perception and road accidents. The survey was designed to collect both quantitative (e.g., multiple choice questions, Likert scale) and qualitative (e.g., open-ended questions) data.

2. Sampling methods. Appropriate sampling methods are important to ensure that survey results are representative of the target population. Different sampling methods such as random, stratified, and quota were used to select different groups of drivers to participate.

3. Data collection. Surveys are conducted through a variety of means, including online platforms, telephone interviews, and face-to-face interviews. Each method has its advantages and limitations, and the choice depends on factors such as population size, available resources, and research objectives. I used online surveys and face-to-face interviews to collect data from different drivers.

4. Data analysis. Once the survey data is collected, it must be analyzed to obtain meaningful information. I used the method of descriptive statistical analysis to identify aspects, relationships and significant factors associated with the risk of accidents. Advanced statistical tools such as factor analysis or modeling by structural equations can also be used to study complex relationships between variables.

5. Risk assessment: Based on the results of the survey and data analysis, I developed risk assessment models that take into account various factors associated with accidents. By quantifying the level of risk, the relevant road organization specialists can prioritize and plan measures for the effective use of resources.

6. Recommendations and measures: The results of the survey and risk assessment serve as the basis for the development of targeted measures to reduce the risk of accidents. These recommendations may include educational programs, improvements to road safety infrastructure, or policy changes to address risk factors identified by survey data.

Improving the information and analytical assessment of accidents is an important area of research aimed at improving measures to ensure road safety. Accurate accident risk assessments allow government, transport authorities and researchers to identify key factors influencing the number of road fatalities and develop effective prevention strategies. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) [11,12] is a widely used research method and tool to help systematically assess and prioritize different risk factors.

Figure 3. Flow chart of matrix assessment of accident risk factors.

Advantages of the AHP in assessing the risk of death on the road:

1. **Structured decision-making:** AHP provides a systematic approach to decision-making, comprehensively analyzes risk factors and their relative significance.
2. **Subjective and objective factors:** AHP allows you to combine both subjective judgments and objective data, providing a balanced assessment of risk factors.
3. **Flexibility:** AHP can solve complex problems on the road according to several criteria. It is flexible and can adapt to hierarchical or weighted results as new data becomes available.
4. **Transparency and communication:** AHP provides a transparent decision-making framework that allows stakeholders to understand the rationale for prioritizing risks. This facilitates communication and consensus building between experts and decision makers.

Figure 4. Flowchart for organizing an expert group survey.

Benefits of a road safety audit (RSA) [13,14]:

1. **Systematic approach:** The RSA follows a systematic and standardized approach to identifying safety concerns and proposing appropriate measures. This ensures that safety assessments are comprehensive and consistent and lead to targeted interventions.
2. **Data-driven decision making:** RSA relies on data collection and analysis to identify risk factors and prioritize safety improvements. This data-driven approach helps allocate resources efficiently and supports evidence-based decision-making.

3. Improving safety: RSA can identify potential safety hazards before accidents occur. By actively solving these problems, the RSA algorithm prevents accidents and reduces the severity of injuries (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Recommended block-scheme on conducting road safety audit process.

RESULTS

An online survey was conducted among 384 drivers in Tashkent using Google Forms. According to statistics from the Republic of Uzbekistan, as of January 1, 2022, 3051.7 thousand vehicles were registered for individuals. A random sampling method was used to select the required number of participants, and it was determined that 384 participants were needed to conduct the survey. When developing the content of the questionnaire questions, the results of foreign studies were studied and 26 questions were initially created. An additional 18 questions were formed taking into account the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan and a total of 41 questions were drawn up.

When polled by participant gender: male-89.5%, female-10.5%; By age: 18-22 years old-3.3%, 23-38 years old-43.1%, 39-54 years old-39.2%, 55-70 years old-14.1% and over 70 years old-0.3%; By profession: employees of state bodies - 17.6%, law enforcement officers - 1.3%, employees of defense structures - 1.6%; employees of educational institutions - 10.8%, employees of public organizations - 13.4%, passengers and cargo carriers - 6.5%, entrepreneurs - 32.4%, students - 4.2% and official unemployed - 12.1%; By education: secondary-5.6%, secondary specialized-23.9%, higher-68.3% and doctors of science (PhD) -2.3%. The 37 factors used are structured as questions, and the driver assesses the importance of the factors by answering "yes" or "no" to indirect questions. The Cochran's Q-test was used to test for a statistically significant effect of the results because this test is appropriate for the corresponding binary data samples.

This study used 37 factors (41 in total) related to road traffic accident, which took into account many aspects, such as driver experience, reaction, confidence, alcohol consumption, etc., developed with the help of the Cochran's Q-test, the following important factors were identified that affect the occurrence of accidents from the point of view of drivers: non-compliance with driving distance or traffic lights, fatigue behind the wheel, family conflicts and problems at work, use of a mobile device while driving, nervousness from external influences while driving, weather conditions, sudden switching of cars from one lane to another, standing in traffic jams were assessed as important factors affecting the risk of accidents on road traffic (Table 2).

Table 2. Level of most important factors by Q-criterion

Factors	Q-criterion
Not keeping the distance while driving or when settling in	80,5

front of a traffic light	
Intersection passage with flashing yellow traffic light	80,1
Adverse weather conditions (fog, rain, snow, dust storm)	76,2
Continuous lane change	71,2
Traffic congestion	68,6
Stressful state from family quarrels or from problems at work	61,4

The causes of accidents are different, but the main reason is that there is an imbalance in the system consisting of people (drivers), vehicles, roads and environmental factors. The following “D-V-R-E” (*Driver – Vehicle – Road – Environment*) system factors were selected (Table 3) [16]:

1. “*Driver*” factors. Drivers are the most active factor in ensuring road safety. According to statistics, in 2022, 26 accidents occurred on the Tashkent Bypass Road 4R21, including 16 collisions with other vehicles, 6 collisions with barriers, 3 collisions with pedestrians and 1 collision with a cyclist. As a result, more than 10 people died. In most cases, the accident was caused by the driver's behavior.

2. “*Vehicle*” factors. The car is the main means of modern transport. The quality of vehicle performance plays an important role in road safety. The immediate cause of road accidents can be problems such as brake failure and other mechanical failures due to late technical inspection.

3. “*Road*” factors. As the main elements of the road, the technical and operational condition of the road, the level of equipment and traffic conditions should not be neglected. Road conditions are a combination of important factors affecting the comfort and safety of road users.

4. “*Environment*” factors. Weather conditions such as fog, heavy rain, snow, icy roads, dust storms and darkness are important factors affecting road safety. Adverse weather is often the cause of accidents and its importance cannot be denied.

Table 3. Classification of selected factors by “D-V-R-E” system

Category	Factors	
Driver	Floor	Failure to maintain a safe distance between vehicles
	Age	Driving through a red light
	Driving experience	Non-compliance with pedestrian priority
	Seat belt non-use	Non-compliance with road signs
	Driving at high speed	Tiredness or falling asleep at the wheel
	Improper overtaking	
	Driving under the influence of alcohol or drugs	
Vehicle	Vehicle type	Vehicle headlight defects
	Vehicle model and make	Side and rear mirrors malfunction
	Vehicle size and weight	Presence of tyre defects
	Car body color	Faults in brake system
	Late maintenance	Fault in control system
Road	Road category	Condition of road surface
	Road section where there is an intersection, intersections, junction	Condition of road signs
	Low road capacity	Insufficient protection of the road section being repaired
	Missing or insufficient shoulder width	Low visibility on the road
		Other objects or animals on the

	Lack of road lighting	road
Environment	Season Day of the week Time of day Fog Dust storm	Snowfall Heavy rain Strong wind Scorching heat

The relative importance of the selected factors is determined using the comparison matrix in Table 4, where each factor is compared with all other factors [17].

Table 4. Comparison matrix

	Criterion 1	Criterion 2	Criterion 3
Criterion 1	$A_{11}=1$	A_{12}	A_{13}
Criterion 2	A_{21}	$A_{22}=1$	A_{23}
Criterion 3	A_{31}	A_{32}	$A_{33}=1$

Using hierarchical analysis, the level of importance of factors within the “D-V-R-E” criteria was assessed (Fig. 6). As a result, the experts determined the weight level of each factor and the compatibility limit of mutual assessments (Tables 5,6,7,8).

“Driver” criterion

“Vehicle” criterion

“Road” criterion

“Environment” criterion

Figure 6. Graph of factors assessed by the expert group.

Table 5. “Driver” criterion.

Criterion	Title	Weight Index	+/-
Criterion 1	Age	2,5%	1,0%
Criterion 2	Driving experience	2,0%	0,9%
Criterion 3	Riding at high speed	19,9%	9,1%
Criterion 4	Driving under alcohol/drug intoxication	18,5%	7,4%
Criterion 5	Insufficient distance between the vehicle	2,7%	1,2%
Criterion 6	Wrong overtaking	2,8%	1,3%
Criterion 7	Running a red light	20,3%	8,1%
Criterion 8	Do not give priority to pedestrians	12,5%	4,6%
Criterion 9	Non-compliance with other road signs	13,9%	5,3%
Criterion 10	The state of fatigue and sleepiness during movement	4,9%	2,1%

Table 6. “Vehicle” criterion.

Criterion	Title	Weight Index	+/-
Criterion 1	Type of vehicle	2,6%	1,3%
Criterion 2	Delayed transport service	15,7%	6,1%
Criterion 3	Malfunction of the headlamp	5,2%	2,5%
Criterion 4	Malfunction of the side mirrors and rear view	3,5%	1,9%
Criterion 5	Tyre wear	14,1%	5,2%
Criterion 6	Malfunction of the brake system	30,8%	8,4%

Criterion 7	Malfunction of the steering system	28,1%	10,5%
Criterion 8	Type of vehicle	2,6%	1,3%
Criterion 9	Delayed transport service	15,7%	6,1%
Criterion 10	Malfunction of the headlamp	5,2%	2,5%

Table 7. "Road" criterion.

Criterion	Title	Weight Index	+/-
Criterion 1	The intersection and the intersection	10,6%	3,4%
Criterion 2	Insufficient road capacity	4,8%	2,4%
Criterion 3	Insufficient shoulder width	2,3%	0,8%
Criterion 4	The weak illumination of the road	15,8%	6,7%
Criterion 5	Bumpy road	18,2%	8,6%
Criterion 6	Malfunction of the road signs	13,0%	2,5%
Criterion 7	Repair sections of the road	11,7%	2,9%
Criterion 8	The lack of road markings	12,5%	2,4%
Criterion 9	The presence of animals on the road or other objects	11,0%	3,9%
Criterion 10	The intersection and the intersection	10,6%	3,4%

Table 8. "Environment" criterion.

Criterion	Title	Weight Index	+/-
Criterion 1	Day of the week	1,7%	0,8%
Criterion 2	Time of day	2,7%	1,2%
Criterion 3	Fog	13,5%	6,9%
Criterion 4	Snowfall	12,6%	6,9%
Criterion 5	Rain	5,7%	2,4%
Criterion 6	Shower	11,1%	8,0%
Criterion 7	Strong wind	7,6%	3,6%
Criterion 8	Dust storm	10,7%	6,1%
Criterion 9	Ice-covered ground	27,4%	13,0%
Criterion 10	Heat	7,0%	3,1%

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the obtained patterns and analysis results, it is possible to develop effective tools for influencing the transport system. This is possible both at the operational level of management - through the introduction of corrective measures and operational measures, and in the long term - through the improvement of development strategies and traffic management. Based on the results of the study, a flow chart of the information and analytical assessment of the risk of accidents in road traffic was proposed, taking into account an integrated approach (Figure 10).

In this study, the development of conceptually new approaches to assessing accident risks is of particular importance. This contributes to improving the efficiency of public administration, allows optimizing traffic management processes and strengthens the basis for the introduction of modern management solutions in the field of road safety. One of the most important approaches

to assessing the risk of accidents on various sections of roads is the road safety audit, as it is considered a systematic process of assessing the road infrastructure in order to identify potential risks that can lead to accidents and develop recommendations for their elimination. This tool is actively used to improve road safety at all stages of the design, construction and operation of roads in developed countries of the world.

In addition to these fundamental principles to reduce road mortality and injuries, effective bills are needed, the correct organization of road traffic, as well as more extensive social education of the population on traffic rules (propaganda of traffic rules in the media, social networks, advertising banners, regular publications, etc.) [19, 20].

Figure 10. Flow chart of information and analytical assessment of road accident risk in road traffic.

The presented results in the four main areas of road safety measures illustrate the following facts:

- Speed violation is a key risk factor for road injuries; due to violation of the speed limit, both the likelihood of an accident and the risk of severe consequences increase. Effective speed control measures, such as establishing and enforcing speed limits, calming traffic through special road design and other methods, and improving vehicle safety technologies, must be implemented everywhere. All four countries have speed limit rules, but speed limits are different, and in some countries it is desirable to further reduce the set speed.

- A significant reduction in could be facilitated by the widespread introduction of more modern vehicle safety technologies, including both passive and active safety systems, based on the implementation of a set of measures, such as unification.

According to the results of the study, it was concluded that without an integrated approach, reducing accidents in road traffic will not give an effective result. Therefore, it is necessary to create a state integrated system that can plan, manage, monitor and improve the field of road safety, taking into account all “D-V-R-E” systems. Such a system should ensure the integration of all elements of road infrastructure, transport, regulations and technologies. This system will require

the introduction of modern data monitoring and analysis technologies, the use of information platforms for the exchange of data between various public and private structures, as well as the development of a system of training and advanced training of drivers. Particular attention should be paid to the prevention of road accidents, improving the state of the road network, as well as introducing innovative solutions to improve vehicle safety. Thus, an integrated road safety system should ensure effective interaction of all components aimed at reducing accidents and increasing the level of safety for all road users.

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